

Complexation Study of In(III), Al(III), Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ni(II) with a Schiff Base Vanillin-*Tris* Buffer

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Stability constants of In(III), Al(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Hg(II) complexes with a Schiff base vanillin-*tris* buffer (VT) are reported at 35° in aqueous medium. The trend of the stability of the present transition and non transition metal complexes is discussed, and ascribed to the structure of the ligand and positive charge and the electro negativity of the central metal ion.

MUCH interest is paid by recent investigators to the study of co-ordination compounds of transition metals with Schiff bases¹, as many of these compounds are pharmaceutically applicable^{2,3}. The present study deals with the potentiometric determination of the stability constants of In(III), Al(III), Cu(II), Hg(II) and Ni(II) complexes with a Schiff base derived from vanillin and *tris* buffer (VT). A 1:1 complex is formed in each case in the aqueous medium at 35.0(±0.1)° and ionic strength $\mu=0.1$.

The preparation and characteristics of the ligand VT are described in the earlier work⁴. The instrumentation and experimental technique are the same as reported elsewhere⁵.

Experimental

Three sets were prepared: (i) 0.01M HClO₄, (ii) 0.01M HClO₄+0.005M ligand and (iii) 0.01M HClO₄+0.005M ligand+ x mM metal salt solution. (Where, $x=1.0$ for Al and In, and $x=1.5$ for all other metals). Requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to the sets to maintain the ionic strength constant $\mu=0.1$. The above sets were titrated against standard carbonate free 0.5M NaOH at a constant temperature 35.0±0.1°.

Results and Discussion

The ligand proton stability constant and the metal-ligand formation constants were determined using the half integral method as described by Rossotti and Irving^{6,7}. The number of the displaceable protons⁷, Y , for the ligand vanillin-*tris* buffer is 1 as seen in its structure⁸ as there is an -OH (phenolic) in vanillin. Hence one may think that the ligand proton formation function $\bar{n}_A=2$ as in a totally protonated ligand, second proton is in the

$\text{>C}=\overset{\text{+}}{\underset{\text{H}}{\text{N}}}$ -group. As a matter of fact, in the presence

of metal ions, the alcoholic -OH group of *tris* buffer also dissociates. If this dissociation is not considered in the calculation, absurd values are obtained for the Bjerrum's formation function, \bar{n} . Of course, the alcoholic proton remains un-dissociated during the acid+ligand titration, hence the ligand proton formation curve \bar{n}_A vs pH extends from 1 to 3. The complex formation curve \bar{n} vs pL extends from 0 to 1 in each case indicating the formation of a 1:1 complex only. The stability constants are determined by the interpolation at half \bar{n} value (Table-1).

The stability constants of Cu(II) and Hg(II) with the ligand salicylaldehyde *tris* buffer (ST) have been reported in our earlier work⁵. The order of stability of Cu and Hg complexes with these two ligands is Cu ST>Cu VT and Hg ST>Hg VT. The ligand ST forms more stable complexes than VT, with Al(III), In(III), and Ni(II) also (ref.9). The higher complexing power in ligand ST arises from the position of the -OH group of salicylaldehyde, which forms an additional bond to the central metal ion, while the present ligand VT, has the phenolic -OH far enough to have any significance in the metal ligand bonding.

In Table-1, it is observed that the complexes InVT and Al-VT are far more stable than the transition metal complexes. This fact can be explained on the basis of Schwarzenbach¹⁰ grouping of metal

TABLE-1

Metal ion	\log/β_H^*	ΔG k.cal/mole
H ⁺	14.52	-20.46
Al ³⁺	5.68	- 8.01
In ³⁺	6.27	- 8.84
Cu ²⁺	3.57	- 5.03
Hg ²⁺	1.83	- 2.58
Ni ²⁺	2.04	- 2.88

$$\begin{aligned} * \log/\beta_H &= \log k_1 + \log k_2 \\ &= 7.85 + 6.67 \\ &= 14.52 \end{aligned}$$

ions. According to it, Al(III) is designated the A-cations group and the greater stability of Al-VT is due to the small size and high positive charge of the Al ion (+3), while In(III) can be designated the B-cations group and its high stability is considered due to the high positive charge and high electronegativity. This fact also accounts for the stability of In-VT > Al-VT.

To explain the order of stability in the remaining three complexes, i.e. CuVT > NiVT > HgVT, the higher stability of Cu(II) is ascribed to back double bonding while relatively less stability of Hg VT complex is due to larger ionic radius of Hg²⁺.

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